

Workflow for 3D modeling of compliant actuators for active exoskeletons

L. Bergmann^{1*}, C. Moazzami¹, S. Leonhardt¹, and C. Ngo¹

¹ Medical Information Technology, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: bergmann@hia.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract: Compliant actuators in exoskeletons for the lower extremities are increasingly used due to the smooth coupling between robot and patient. However, serial compliant actuators place higher demands on the model and control. For this reason, we present a workflow that allows 3D multi-domain modeling of the dynamic system. First, a 3D static model is designed in SolidWorks, then exported to Simscape and extended with the dynamic properties. The workflow is exemplified for a variable stiffness actuator. The model shows a high correlation to the system and can be used for further controller designs.

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I. Introduction

Research on exoskeletons for augmenting the human body began as early as the 1960s with the development of the Hardiman [1]. However, only the development of more powerful computers and motors enabled research in this area to establish itself as an important, interdisciplinary field combining robotics, sensor technology, control, medicine, and bionics. In particular, the development of actuators for exoskeletons in rehabilitation therapy for patients with partial residual functions, such as after a stroke, is a major challenge. The reason is the requirement of the structural design between robot and patient. Shi et al describe the ideal rehabilitation robot as a rigid-flexible soft hybrid structure [2]. For this reason, compliant actuators have been investigated, which are characterized by series elasticity between the actuator and patient [3], [4]. Variable stiffness actuators also have the advantage that the elasticity can be adapted to the diverse requirements of the gait by changing the spring constant [5]. Although the serial elasticity allows a soft coupling to the patient, such actuators have higher complexity in the hardware design and demand higher requirements for the modeling and control of the system. For this reason, we present a workflow that enables 3D multi-domain modeling of such systems. The proposed workflow is exemplified by the Mechanical Rotary Variable Impedance Actuator (MeRIA), which was already presented in [6] and [7]. The obtained model can be used to design and validate torque, position and impedance controllers for compliant actuators.

II. Material and methods

The workflow starts with the 3D modeling of the drive using a CAD program (SolidWorks, Dassault Systèmes, Vélizy-Villacoublay, France). The created model is then exported to MATLAB Simscape (MathWorks, Massachusetts, USA), where the functionality of the dynamic components is added.

II.I. Design in 3D-CAD-Programm (Solidworks)

When designing the drive, bodies that are fixed to each other should be defined as separate assemblies. Rotational

or translational degrees of freedom between the assemblies can be set in SolidWorks for illustration and placement, but these must be replaced in Simscape later. Furthermore, properties such as mass distributions and material density must already be taken into account in this step to reproduce inertia moments correctly.

The MeRIA drive has a Maxon EC 60 motor as the main drive, coupled to two leaf springs via a harmonic drive (HD). The leaf springs' effective length can be varied via a second motor using a leadscrew and a slider. Four cam followers are attached to the slider, which transfers the contact force to the output shaft and subsequently to the human joint. The assemblies designed in SolidWorks, including the casing of the HD, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 3D modeling of MeRIA components in Solidworks

II.II. Dynamic modeling in Simscape

After exporting the assemblies to Solidworks using the Simscape Multibody Link plug-in, the assemblies are available as subsystems with connection ports. The next step is to implement the degrees of freedom between the assemblies using rotational, translational and the lead screw joints.

Figure 2: Modelling of HD, length discretized leaf springs and DC motors in Simscape.

As shown in Figure 2, the two motors' functionality and the gears are realized in the electrical and rotational domain. The required motor parameters (armature resistance & inductance and torque constant) and gear parameters (transmission ratio, friction) were obtained from the datasheets. The torques applied by the motors are directly transmitted to the respective motor shafts. Ideal torque and rotational speed sensors realize the domain change from the rotational domain to the SimMechanics blocks.

We realized the modeling of the spring properties entirely in Simscape. For this, we used the Multibody Flexible Body Library (v4.0) as a basis for the MeRIA example. This library models the spring properties using a length discretized implementation. The exact properties of the spring can be adjusted by entering the material properties (Density, Modulus of Elasticity, Shear Modulus, and Damping Factor). In this model, however, forces can only be applied to the uppermost and lowermost elements. To change the effective length during the simulation, an additional extension of the model was therefore necessary. Through the so-called geometry export of all spring elements, it is possible to model the springs and the Cam Followers' contact forces.

III. Results and discussion

Current steps of 1A and 2A were applied to Motor 1 at different effective lengths to validate the dynamic behavior of the model. In both the model and the actual system, an additional load (4 kg, 54 cm) was used to simulate the lower leg. Figure 3 shows the measured and simulated torque over the springs for the example with the highest stiffness. The root-mean-square error is 1.28 Nm. However, the accuracy decreases at higher input currents.

We extended the second motor of the real and the simulated system by identical PI speed controllers to validate the second motor's dynamical behavior and the stiffness adjustment via the lead screw. Subsequently, different reference speeds were applied. In Figure 4, only minimal deviations between the system and the model can be seen.

Figure 3: Validation of Motor 1; Top: Current, Bottom: Measured and simulated spring torque

Figure 4: Validation of Motor 2 with identical velocity controllers

IV. Conclusion

The proposed approach for modeling compliant actuators can reduce costly hardware tests and make it possible to quickly and efficiently implement controls without access to the hardware. In addition, the modeling approach can be extended to include other components, enabling the simulation of the entire exoskeleton.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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